

PERFORMANCE OF WIRE MESH GASKETS WITH AIR-INFLATABLE CORE

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Abstract

We are investigating the performance of a prototype wire mesh electromagnetic interference (EMI) gasket with an inflatable core. The gasket is constructed of several layers of wire mesh woven around an air-inflatable rubber core. The wire mesh is made of tin-coated copper-clad steel. Results of short-term experiments show promising performance and future applications.

Introduction

Before the shielding effectiveness (SE) of a tactical shelter to a high-altitude electromagnetic pulse (HEMP) can be determined, the shelter must be carefully examined for its ability to attenuate HEMP fields. This process is very expensive and time-consuming with conventional HEMP simulators. The situation is worsened by the large number of shelters which require HEMP hardening and testing. Recently, in their studies of the S280C shelter, authors have established a correlation between the shelter's SE under HEMP and under continuous wave (cw) excitations [1]. This means that HEMP SE testing can be replaced with an inexpensive test method using a cw source and conventional instrumentation. The HEMP SE can then be estimated from the correlation data. The correlation, however, must be established for each type of shelter.

During the course of this effort, it was discovered that the currently used mesh gasket with polymer core failed to meet its performance requirements in two to three months after initial gasket installation. The cause of this failure was a compression set of the polymer core [2]. An exhaustive market search was conducted to identify a more suitable gasket core material. As a result of this search, several core materials were located and considered for testing. Although testing has not been completed, the air-inflatable core shows greatly improved performance over the polymer core gaskets presently used in the shelters.

An S280C shelter was used to test the performance of the air-inflatable wire mesh gasket. The S280C is a tactical

shelter whose exterior dimensions are about 7 1/4 (h) by 7 1/4 (w) by 12 (l) ft with a tare weight of 1400 lb. The shelter is a double-skinned metallic enclosure. Walls are constructed of two aluminum panels bonded to rigid urethane foam. There is a 2-1/4 in. separation between the inner and outer skins where structural members have been placed. Rivets were used to join the panels and structural members. Figure 1 shows a cutaway view of the door and latch of an S280C shelter. Mesh gaskets are not shown, but their location is marked with an "*".

The S280C shelter was chosen because it has the least number of penetrations among the Department of Defense (DoD) standard family of tactical shelters. The major penetrations, including the door and escape hatch/air vent, are on the back wall. The remaining penetrations consist of only the drain hole and riveted seams. The door has four hinges and closes to a specified 30 ft-lb using three latch arm assemblies. The escape hatch has a louver and a honeycomb, which attenuates lights and electromagnetic fields while allowing air to ventilate. The honeycomb is attached behind the louver with screws, a strip of metal, and a thin strip of tin-coated, copper-clad steel gasket. The perimeters of the door and hatch have two grooves each. The inner and outer grooves are used to mount EMI gaskets and environmental gaskets, respectively.

Six brand-new S280C shelters have been tested in recent years. These tests show that major EMI/EMP penetration areas are the gasketed door and hatch seams. All the riveted seams showed SE values around 80 dB. The escape hatch/air vent provides at least 60-dB attenuation with a honeycomb and louver assembly. This area is further shielded with a metallic cover hinged on one side and latched on the remaining three sides.

Prototype Layout

A cross section of the core of the inflatable gasket is shown in figure 2. This non-reinforced silicone rubber core was then wrapped with five layers of tin-coated, copper-clad steel wire mesh. The gasket was manufactured with the

Figure 1. Cutaway view of door and hatch of S280C shelter. Mesh gaskets are not shown, but locations are marked with an "*".

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Test Procedure

proper dimensions to be installed directly into the gasket retaining areas of the door and hatch. A single air supply was used to inflate both door and hatch gaskets, thus assuring that the pressure of both gaskets was equal. For the prototype testing the air supply was a small high-pressure bottle which was then regulated down to the desired pressure. This setup gave the necessary versatility to assess the gasket's performance at different air pressures. Figure 3 shows a diagram of the setup.

Figure 2. Cutaway view of air-inflated gasket showing mesh gasket and nozzle.

Figure 3. Prototype layout of wire mesh gasket with air-inflatable core.

A modified MIL-STD-285 test procedure was used to evaluate the wire mesh air-inflatable gaskets. There is a general concern with the repeatability of the test results of a traditional MIL-STD-285 test. It is not uncommon to have 15-dB variations at a given test point in day-to-day measurements. To attain test data which were reliable and repeatable it was necessary to modify the way traditional MIL-STD-285 testing was conducted. This included such things as establishing fixed test points along seams and gasketed areas. Also, hard wire penetrations were eliminated to avoid any stray coupling inside the shelter. It is strongly recommended, if it is necessary to pass signal or power cables through the shielded enclosure, that they be filtered and terminated properly. The cable penetration area should then be tested for proper shielding. Likewise, to minimize any cross talk, semirigid coaxial cables should be used, and electrostatically shielded loops will minimize E-field coupling. The current on the transmitting loop should remain constant for a given frequency between the reference measurement and the test measurement, insuring proper field strengths. The planes of the loops should be placed perpendicular to the seam at any given test point to insure worst-case SE values. It is beneficial to use mechanical nonmetallic stands to hold the loops in the proper position while the attenuation is being measured.

The test setup used is shown in figure 4. A reference measurement was made with the two 12-in.-diam electrostatically shielded loops placed outside the shelter with a clear space of at least 20 ft. The loops were placed 24 in. apart (plus the thickness of the shield) and positioned in a coplanar orientation. The swept output of the network analyzer was transmitted to the 100-W power amplifier via a fiber optic link. The amplified signal was then used to drive the transmitting loop. The induced signal on the receiving loop was amplified with a 20-dB small signal amplifier at the input to the network analyzer. This measured signal was normalized so that any further measurements would indicate the change in the signal from the reference measurement. A test measurement was then made by positioning the loops at the appropriate test locations (receiving loop inside shelter,

Figure 4. Equipment layout for CW SE measurement.

transmitting loop outside shelter) and measuring signal attenuation. The separation distance between the reference and test measurements was maintained, and the plane of the loop was positioned perpendicular to the seam at any given test point. The inverse of this attenuation value was then defined as the shielding effectiveness. All signal cables were semirigid coaxial cables, and type-N connectors were used whenever possible. This test procedure proved in past studies to be very reliable. Tests exhibited variations in shielding effectiveness measurements on stable shielding enclosures of only ± 1 dB over several months of testing. This SE can be defined as

$$SE = 20 \log_{10} H^e/H^i$$

where H^e is the reference measurement described in the previous section and H^i is the test measurement also described in the previous section. The location of the different test points is shown in figure 5, which is a view of the shelter rear wall, containing the door and hatch.

Figures 6 and 7 show the measured SE at the center (loop positioned vertically) and top center of the door), respectively. The SE values were measured as functions of frequency and air pressure showing a 20-dB per decade

Figure 5. Test point locations used for assessing EMI performance of air-inflatable wire mesh gasket.

increase irrespective of the air pressure and test point location. All test points exhibited similar shielding characteristics as functions of frequency and air pressure. Discrete shielding values for the different test points are shown in table 1. Test points 37 showed the worst SE values because it is so close to two major seams—the door and the hatch.

Examination of the data shows that the actual shielding performance of the gasket could be improved with a larger inflatable core. At 10 psi the gasket was essentially fully inflated (see fig. 2); any increase in pressure from this point only hardened the core. A slightly larger core would provide more contact pressure over a larger area of the mating surfaces, thus increasing contact resistance and shielding performance.

It should be noted that all testing was performed in an environmentally controlled area. The purpose was to examine the core material for compression set and not to test the wire mesh material for galvanic corrosive performance.

Conclusion

MIL-STD-907B requires that military tactical shelters shall meet 60-dB SE when tested in accordance with MIL-STD-285. MIL-STD-285 requires electric, magnetic, and plane wave testing from 150 kHz to 10 GHz. Experience has shown that a magnetic field measurement at the lower frequency will always produce the worst-case SE due to the wave impedance. The inflatable rubber core wire mesh gasket has shown shielding values approaching 70 dB at this frequency, and it is expected that this could be improved with a larger core. The cost of the prototype gasket was relatively expensive; however, this cost was influenced largely by the number of layers of wire mesh (five on the prototype). It is believed that this number can be reduced to at most two by use of a larger rubber core. The high-pressure air bottles, regulator, and gauges could also be replaced with a simple, less expensive setup once a final gasket configuration is decided upon.

Figure 6. SE of S280C at center of door (loop positioned vertically) for five layers of mesh gasket with air-inflatable core.

Figure 7. SE of S280C at top center of door for five layers of mesh gasket with air-inflatable core.

Table 1. CW SE of S280C shelter.

TEST POINT	FREQUENCIES Hz			
	150 K	1.0 M	5 M	10 M
05 V	75	94	110	115
05 H	70	91	106	112
37 H	67	88	103	109
23 V	68	88	100	107
46 H	70	88	101	107

Air pressure = 20 psi

Gasket = air-inflatable with five layers of mesh gasket

References

- [1] Y. M. Lee, J. Latess, and B. T. Benwell, Establishing a Correlation of Shelter Shielding Effectiveness Between Hemp and CW Excitations, presented at the Sixth NEM Symposium, Menlo Park, CA (May 16-19 1988).
- [2] Y. M. Lee and B. T. Benwell, Simulated High-Altitude Electromagnetic Pulse Test on DoD Standard Family of Tactical Shelters—Part 1: Analysis, U.S. Army Laboratory Command, Harry Diamond Laboratories, HDL-TR-2104 (July 1988).